

Composition and Stability Constant of the Interaction Product of Fe(III) and 3-Nitrophthalimide in Methanolic Medium

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pH-metric, conductometric and amperometric studies of ferric 3-nitrophthalimide systems in methanolic medium indicate the formation of two complexes; 1 : 4 complex at a *pH* 9 to 10 and the 1 : 2 complex at *pH* 8 to 8.5. The stability constant of the complex was determined by Bjerrum's method. The values of the stability constants were found to be $\log k_1 = 5.19$, $\log k_2 = 4.38$, $\log k_3 = 3.57$, $\log k_4 = 2.76$ and $\log K = 15.90$. The value of $-\Delta F$ at 30° was found to be 21.97 K.cals/mole. The chemical analysis of the isolated complex show the formation of $KFe(C_8H_3N_2O_4)_4 (CH_3OH)_2$ complex. I.R. spectra show the existence of metal-oxygen bond. The complex is paramagnetic in character.

Heavy metal imides are unstable in aqueous medium but they can be stabilised if the reactions are carried out in methanolic solutions. Survey of the existing literature reveals that no physico-chemical study has been made to elucidate the nature and composition of these complexes; hence a comprehensive study of the complexes of 3-nitrophthalimide with different metals was undertaken by us. The present paper deals with our study of the complex formed with Fe(III).

Preliminary observations gave the following results : (i) with higher concentration of the complexing agent, a yellow precipitate, susceptible to water was obtained (*pH* for the onset of precipitation ≈ 9.0), (ii) with higher concentration of ferric chloride, a soluble complex, dark red in colour was obtained at *pH* higher than the *pH* for the onset of precipitation of ferric hydroxide (*pH* ≈ 3.5).

The composition and stability of the two complexes using *pH* metric, conductometric, amperometric, and I.R. spectral technique was determined. The isolation and analysis of the complex was also carried out. Magnetic properties of the isolated complexes were also studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-nitrophthalimide (M.P. 216°) was prepared in the pure form by the interaction of urea on 3-nitrophthalic¹ acid in the laboratory. Ferric chloride of Analar grade was used for the preparation of stock solution. Potassium hydroxide, lithium chloride, copper sulphate, potassium sulphate, salicylic acid and sulphuric acid used in the estimation of nitrogen were of Analar quality.

All experiments were performed at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. *pH* measurements were made with a Beckmann model H *pH* meter with glass electrode. The electrode was kept immersed

1. G. Ya. Kandrat and Chill-Heng Huang, *Zhur Priklad Khim.*, 1962, **35**, 199-201.

in the methanol for several days before use as recommended by Zeidler². Fritz³ also recommended the use of ordinary glass electrode for titrations in non-aqueous medium. The pH meter was standardised using potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer of pH 4.0. Conductivity measurements were carried out with Phillips conductivity bridge using a dip type conductivity cell.

Amperometric titrations were carried out with the help of Toshniwal manual polarograph type CLO-2 using Pye Scalamp Galvanometer in the external circuit. Purified hydrogen was used for deaeration. A Fisher capillary with a drop time of 3.4 sec. (open circuit) was used for d.m.e. The capillary constant ($m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$) was 1.877. Lithium chloride was used as the supporting electrolyte. No maxima suppressor was required in the present system.

Infra red spectra in nujol phase were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 137-1281 spectrophotometer.

The susceptibility was obtained by Gouy method at room temperature. The tube was calibrated with A.R. tetraaquo copper (II) sulphate monohydrate.

FIG. 1

Curve No.	FeCl ₃ (ml) (0.05M)	Ligand (ml) (0.05 M)	FeCl ₃ : Ligand
I	3	0	1 : 0
II	3	3	1 : 1
III	3	6	1 : 2
IV	3	9	1 : 3
V	3	12	1 : 4
VI	3	15	1 : 5

Total volume was made up to 20 ml in each case and then titrated with standard KOH.

- H. Zeidler, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **146**, 251.
- J. S. Fritz, *Acid-Base Titration in non-aqueous solvents*, G. F. Smith Chemical Co.; Columbus, Ohio, 1952, p. 11.

A stock solution of hydrated ferric chloride ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was prepared in redistilled methanol and was standardised iodometrically⁴ and then diluted with methanol. Stock solutions of 3-nitrophthalimide, lithium chloride and potassium hydroxide were also prepared in methanol and were diluted to the desired concentration with methanol as needed.

Optimum pH for the formation of the complex: In order to verify whether hydrogen ions were liberated during complex ion formation, pH metric titrations of the mixture of ferric chloride and 3-nitrophthalimide in the ratio 1 : 0, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4, 1 : 5 against 0.1M KOH were made (Fig. 1); downward shift in pH in the order 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 4, and 1 : 5 was observed above pH 9.2, and it was therefore concluded that the formation of the complex would take place above this pH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

pH-metric, conductometric and amperometric titrations: The composition of the complexes was determined by pH-metric, conductometric and amperometric titrations. In the case of both pH-metry and conductometry, direct (20.0 ml. of ferric chloride of conc., 0.0033M and 0.0046M in the cell) and reverse (10.0 ml. of 3-nitrophthalimide of conc., 0.033M, 0.046M, 0.052M and 0.079M in the cell) titration were carried out. The solution of 3-nitrophthalimide was prepared in one equivalent of methanolic KOH to give the potassium salt of 3-nitrophthalimide ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{K}$).

FIG. 2

The ratios obtained by all the three methods were 1 : 4 and 1 : 2 corresponding to Fe(III) : 3-nitrophthalimide. The reactions between Fe(III) and potassium 3-nitrophthalimide can be represented by the following stoichiometric equations,

The nature of the amperometric titration curves carried out at -1.6 to -1.8 V gave unusual titration curves. In direct titrations Fig. (2) (FeCl_3 in the cell), the diffusion current instead of showing an initial decrease, showed a marked increase. This might be due to the decomposition of the complex in higher concentration of the metal. Further addition of imide brought about a decrease in the current and after the ratio 1 : 4 had been realised, it again showed an increase. Reverse titrations Fig. (3) (3-nitrophthalimide in the cell) showed an initial decrease and only when a complexing ratio 1 : 4 was realised then the current showed an increase due to the decomposition of the yellow complex. The next break occurred at the combining ratio 1 : 2 after which the current became almost constant.

FIG. 3

Isolation and analysis: Reactants were mixed keeping a little excess of 3-nitrophthalimide than the calculated amount in order to get the 1 : 4 complex. The pH was maintained at 9.5 to 10 by the addition of methanolic KOH. A thick yellow precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was washed with methyl alcohol and then dried in a desiccator over silica. A weighed amount of the dried sample was digested with concentrated HCl and its iron content estimated gravimetrically by ammonium hydroxide. Potassium and

nitrogen was estimated by flame photometric (Carl Zeiss Model III) and Kjeldahl's⁵ methods. The analysis corresponded to the formula $KFe(C_8H_3N_2O_4)_4(CH_3OH)_2$. Found: potassium 4.1%; iron 5.7%; nitrogen = 13.0%. Calcd.: potassium 4.2%; iron 6.2%; nitrogen = 12.2%.

The I.R. spectra of 3-nitrophthalimide and its 1 : 4 complex with iron (Fig. 4) showed a marked shift in the C=O-stretching frequency from 1700 cm^{-1} (ligand) to 1610 cm^{-1} (complex). This observation provides evidence of metal oxygen binding only.

FIG. 4

Non-polymerisation of the ferric chloride in methanolic medium: Before proceeding to determine the various physico-chemical constants, it was considered necessary to establish that $[Fe(CH_3OH)_6]^{3+}$ does not undergo polymerisation in methanolic solution of *pH* greater than 9.2. The potentiometric method has been recommended for this purpose. On adding methanolic KOH to ferric chloride solution, the *pH* should decrease on standing if it undergoes polymerisation. In our case it has been found that the addition of alkali does not change the *pH* of the ferric chloride solution even if it is allowed to stand for more than fifteen minutes. This behaviour was observed throughout the *pH* range 2 to 12. It was therefore concluded that $[Fe(CH_3OH)_6]^{3+}$ does not undergo polymerisation.

Dissociation constant of the ligand (3-nitrophthalimide): The ligand is a weak acid. Its dissociation constant may be represented as follows:

$$K^* = \frac{(R)^-(H)^+}{(RH)}$$

The constant is determined by measuring the *pH* values of the solutions resulting from progressive additions of a standard alkali to a reagent solution of known strength and from the

formation curve, obtained by plotting nH against pH values (Fig. 5), where nH = average number of hydrogen ions attached to ligand ion.

$$nH = \frac{RH}{R^- + RH} + \frac{R^- - P - H^+ + OH^-}{R^-} \quad \text{where}$$

R = total concentration of the reagent, and P = concentration of alkali added.

The correct value of pK^* is obtained as pH from the curve (Fig. 5) when $nH = 0.5$. Thus the value of K^* was found to be 1×10^{-11} .

10 ml OF 0.05 M 3 NITRO PHTHALIMIDE IS TITRATED WITH 0.1 M KOH

FIG. 5

Stability of the complex: It was determined by Bjerrum's⁶ method. Titration of the methanolic solution of the ligand (0.05M) with and without metal ion (0.01M) was performed against methanolic KOH (0.025M). The results are depicted in (Fig. 6). The values of n , average number of ligand bound per metal ion were evaluated.

At any pH the concentration of the ligand (R)⁻ was calculated as follows :

$$(TR) = (RH) + (R)^- + (FeR)^{++} + 2(FeR_2)^+ + 3(FeR_3) + 4(FeR_4)^- \quad \dots (i)$$

$$(TM) = (Fe)^{3+} + (FeR)^{++} + (FeR_2)^+ + (FeR_3) + (FeR_4)^- \quad \dots (ii)$$

$$(RH) + (R)^- = (TR) - (FeR)^{++} - 2(FeR_2)^+ - 3(FeR_3) - 4(FeR_4)^- \quad \dots (iii)$$

$$(R) + \frac{(R)(H)}{K^*} = TR - (FeR)^{++} - 2(FeR_2)^+ - 3(FeR_3) - 4(FeR_4)^- \quad \dots (iv)$$

$$(R)^- = \frac{(TR) - (FeR)^{++} - 2(FeR_2)^+ - 3(FeR_3) - 4(FeR_4)^-}{1 + \frac{(H)}{K^*}} \quad \dots (v)$$

Where K^* represents the dissociation constant of the ligand. The values of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of $-\log R$ (Fig. 7). As a first approximation the values of $-\log R$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5, 1.5, 2.5$ and 3.5 are equal to $\log k_1 5.4$; $\log k_2 4.2$; $\log k_3 3.5$ and $\log k_4 3.2$ respectively.

FIG. 6

These temporary constants were corrected by Bjerrum's⁷ method of successive approximations applying the formulae

$$\bar{n} = \frac{4 \times 6^{1/4} x^3 KR + 8 \times 6^{1/2} x^4 K^2 R^2 + 6^{3/4} \times 4 x^3 K^3 R^3 + 4 K^4 R^4}{1 + 4 \times 6^{1/4} x^3 KR + 4 \times 6^{1/2} x^4 K^2 R^2 + 6^{3/4} \times 1.33 \times x^3 K^3 R^3 + K^4 R^4} \quad \dots \text{(vi)}$$

FIG. 7

7. Martell and Kalvin, *Chemistry of metal chelates*, 1959, 80-84.

where k = an average constant, and x = spreading factor between two successive formation constants.

Correct values of \bar{n} obtained from this equation for each corresponding value of R were then plotted against $-\log R$ (Fig. 8). Thus a set of \bar{n} and $\log R$, at various values of pH , as calculated from Fig (6), was given in the following table :

TABLE 1

Values of \bar{n} and $-\log R$ corresponding to their pH

pH	n	$-\log R$
7.0	0.6	5.36
7.5	1.0	4.88
8.0	1.3	4.38
8.5	2.3	3.80
9.0	3.2	3.30
9.5	4.0	2.50
10.0	4.0	2.40

FIG. 8

The final values of $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$, $\log k_3$, $\log k_4$ and $\log K$ (over all stability constant) are 5.19, 4.38, 3.67, 2.76 and 15.90 respectively. From these results it is clear that the \bar{n} increases with increase in pH showing thereby that it is the anionic form which takes part in the reaction.

From $\Delta F = -RT \ln K$ where the terms have their usual significance, the value of $-\Delta F$ comes out to be 21.97 K.cals/mole.

The octahedral structure of the complex $KFe(C_8H_3N_2O_4)_4(CH_2OH)_2$ was also supported by magnetic susceptibility measurements⁸, as the effective magnetic moment was found to be 1.7 B.M.

Since the pH scale was described only for aqueous solutions but this study was carried out in methanolic medium, all these constants may be considered as arbitrary values.

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8. Pierce W. Selwood, *Magneto-chemistry*, 1964, 222.